

Thinopyrum distichum Coastal Wheatgrass

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

© D. Richardson

Group: Monocot

Size: 0.5 m in height

Distribution:

The shores of the Western and Eastern Cape Provinces of South Africa.

Importance:

It is the sole species of the genus that occurs in the Southern Hemisphere. It is a wild relative of bread wheat and is a halophyte. If the genes conferring its ability to tolerate high levels of soil salinity can be transferred to commercial wheat, it has the potential to expand wheat production and increase food security.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 227.85 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 13.26 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 10.54 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.5% [Single: 11.3%, Duplicated: 88.0%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 8 949.62 kilobases

Contig number: 3 10⁷

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